

Can we improve the efficiency of livestock production by using technology to facilitate natural behaviour?

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Abstract

There is strong evidence that the behavioural repertoire of modern domestic farm animals includes behaviours inherited from their wild ancestors, especially in terms of dietary choice. Many livestock production systems limit or deny the animals the opportunity to express these natural behaviours, and this can negatively impact on both animal welfare and production efficiency. Precision livestock farming technologies could help facilitate the expression of these instinctive behaviours in commercial farming systems, helping to improve animal welfare and production efficiency.

Introduction

The wild *Bovidae* that were the ancestors of domestic sheep, goats and cattle first appeared approximately 20 million years ago in the early Miocene (Hassanin, 2014). The main farmed ruminant species (sheep, goats and cattle) were domesticated by humans starting approximately twelve thousand years ago as part of the Neolithic revolution (Ryder, 1984). For much of their domestication history, cattle, and to a lesser extent, sheep and goats were largely managed as individuals or in small groups. This often included close human guidance by a 'shepherd' who controlled where the animals foraged and also provided some protection from wild predators (Umstatter, 2011). The intensification of livestock production in developed countries in the second half of the twentieth century resulted in increasing numbers of ruminant livestock being managed in groups, with humans taking increasing control over the animal's environment, diet and reproduction.

This intensification of livestock production led to concerns for animal welfare (Harrison, 1964), and the importance of 'normal' behaviour for animal welfare was recognised and incorporated into one of the Five Freedoms i.e. freedom to express normal behaviour (Farm Animal Welfare Council, 1979). However, as well as impacting on animal welfare, reducing the ability of farm animals to express natural behaviours may also reduce the efficiency of their production. This paper explores this concept and discusses the role that technology might play in promoting natural behaviour in farmed livestock.

Diet selection

A major part of the life of a herbivore is finding, selecting and consuming a diet that meets their specific nutritional requirements. Research has shown that sheep and cattle grazing adjacent monocultures of ryegrass and white clover select mixed diets, typically 70% clover and 30% grass (reviewed by Rutter, 2006). This 70:30 ratio also gives the optimal level of microbial protein synthesis in an artificial rumen (Merry *et al.*, 2002) suggesting that grazing ruminants are selecting a diet that optimises microbial protein synthesis within their rumen. There is also a consistent diurnal pattern to preference, with a stronger preference for clover in the morning, and the proportion of grass in the diet increasing towards the main evening meal (Rutter *et al.*, 2004). Cattle and sheep typically avoid grazing at night, so consuming fibre-rich grass which has a slower passage rate in the evening will help the animals reduce the need to graze during the hours of darkness (Rutter, 2006). It is argued that these diet selection patterns have an evolutionary origin i.e. the need to reduce the risk of predation by minimising the time spent foraging during the day and avoiding it at night if possible (Newman *et al.*, 1995). These patterns are likely to be the result of millions of years of natural selection in the wild ancestors of sheep and cattle, balancing the need to meet their nutritional requirements whilst avoiding being killed by predators (Rutter, 2010).

In agricultural systems, grass and clover are grown in mixed swards which require the grazing animal to search for the desired plant species, and this, as discussed above, changes over the course of the day. Facilitating diet selection (i.e. making it easier for animals to select their preferred plant species by e.g. growing them as spatially separate monocultures) improves production in dairy cattle (Cosgrove *et al.*, 2001) and sheep (Venning *et al.*, 2003). However, managing the grazing of separate grass and clover monocultures is likely to increase rather than decrease the general challenges around the effective management of grazing. The general challenges of grazing have led to increasing numbers of dairy cattle being housed all year around and fed a Total Mixed Ration (TMR). These incorporate concentrate feeds, and need to be thoroughly mixed to prevent the animals 'sorting' i.e. the animals selecting and consuming an excessive amount of concentrates which can lead to ruminal acidosis (Maekawa *et al.*, 2002). Whilst this over-consumption of concentrates challenges the concept that animals have evolved to select optimal diets, the natural environments in which the animals evolved would not have had such large quantities of concentrated nutrients. Indeed, natural selection will have favoured animals that selected the few, limited concentrated sources of nutrients that did occur naturally as this would have helped reduce the time spent foraging and so reduced the risk of predation. However, this presents a problem implementing diet selection in current livestock systems as the animals may make themselves sick through the over-consumption of one of the feeds offered. The current solution i.e. feeding a Total Mixed Ration may cause animal welfare problems, as it prevents the animals from achieving an important goal i.e. selecting their own diet (Manteca *et al.*, 2008; Rutter, 2010). Mixed rations are also likely to reduce the animal's ability to fine tune their diet to meet their specific nutrient requirements and so may lead to more inefficient production and an associated increase in pollution (Rutter, 2010). Potential solutions to this problem other than providing a single mixed ration are discussed later.

Choice of environment

Another area where the intensification of animal production has impacted on animal choice is that most housed systems reduce or even remove the ability of animals to select their own environment in terms of temperature, humidity, solar radiation, rainfall, air/wind speed and lying substrate. Research has shown that many factors affect the preference for pasture *versus* cubicle housing in dairy cattle (reviewed by Charlton and Rutter, 2017). Motupalli *et al.* (2014) demonstrated that cows with pasture access produced 25% more milk compared to those that were continuously housed. Cows with pasture access consumed the same amount of TMR as housed cows but ate it more quickly, and pasture access cows ate on average 1.2kg DM/d grazed grass. This grass intake accounted for approximately half the increased milk yield. It was not clear what accounted for the remaining increase in milk yield, although the higher lying times in the pasture access cows probably play a role. The pasture access cows also had a greater choice of environmental conditions and more space to exhibit natural behaviours, and these factors could have increased comfort, reduced stress and enhanced production.

Using technology to facilitate natural behaviours

One natural behaviour already being facilitated in cattle using technology is self-grooming using rotary brushes. In the wild or extensive systems, livestock rub their bodies against tree trunks or fence posts to help remove ectoparasites and maintain coat condition. Cows prefer automatic rotary brushes over fixed brushes (Gutmann, 2010) presumably as automatic brushes help them groom body regions that would otherwise be hard to reach (DeVries *et al.*, 2007). The use of automatic brushes can, in some cases, increase milk yield (Schukken and Young, 2009).

As discussed earlier, one major challenge with offering animals a free choice to select their own diet is that animals do not always make 'wise' choices and can over-consume concentrates. One potential solution to this problem could be to feed the animals two mixed rations, one, for example, a bit more energy dense and one a bit more protein dense, and then let the animals select a combination of the two that meets their nutritional needs. The intention would be to mimic the choice offered to animals grazing grass and clover. Labour costs mean this approach would probably not be cost effective on traditional farms. However, this could be facilitated using robotic feeding systems (e.g. Lely Vector) which are already being used on a small but growing number of commercial farms. These automatically select, mix and deliver rations on a continuous basis throughout the day. Rumen pH monitoring (using e.g. a smaxTec or eCow rumen pH bolus) in a few sentinel cows could help alert the farmer to any problems with the mixed rations and could help mitigate the potential risk of cows developing ruminal acidosis.

Technology might also help facilitate environmental choice, even in housed systems. Several systems are available (e.g. Smartbow, Nedap) that can track the movements and location of dairy cows in a building, and automated control of ventilation via fans and/or adjustable side screens (e.g. Galebreaker) is also available. It should be possible to combine these two technologies to make a 'smart' building that can adapt to cow behaviour. For example, ventilation could be increased in one part of the building and then the responses of the cows i.e. towards or away from this area could be monitored. The ventilation could then be dynamically controlled based on cow responses, aiming to provide a choice of environment for the cows to hopefully improve cow comfort, welfare and production.

Conclusion

Although thousands of years of domestication have resulted in changes to some aspects of farm animal behaviour, there is strong evidence that domestic livestock retain behaviour patterns that evolved in their wild ancestors over millions of years. There is evidence that by facilitating the expression of these natural, evolutionary behaviours, we can help promote animal welfare, increase the efficiency of livestock production and reduce its environmental impact. Technologies could help achieve this goal by promoting animal choice whilst protecting against behaviours that may otherwise harm the animal. This approach challenges possible misconceptions that precision livestock farming technologies are primarily focussed on the further intensification of livestock production by demonstrating that they can be used to improve both production efficiency and animal welfare by facilitating natural behaviour.

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